

Construction of Knowledge Through Video Resources in Foreign Language Classroom Settings

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Media, Teachers, Students, Video, Educational</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4710696</p>	<p><i>Learning media is a tool to deliver learning material from the teacher to students. Due to the advancement of web 2.0, numerous learning media has many contributions to the teaching and learning process in the classroom, such as YouTube videos, TikTok, Instagram or Snapchat etc. While there continue to be disagreements over the possible benefits and drawbacks of video content, there is also a growing interest in how and whether various video content tools could be used for educational purposes.</i></p> <p><i>This research investigates the experience of using video content (with subtitles or caption) for foreign language learning. We aim to study various methods used for teaching a foreign language using video content using YouTube, Snapchat, TikTok and Instagram etc. We also explore how adding subtitles affect the learning curve of foreign language learners.</i></p> <p><i>This review research shows that teachers and students get positive experiences using videos in classrooms to learn a foreign language. It is observed from the effects of interviews conducted by various authors that the use of videos contributes to the learning process in the classroom. Additionally, the students' questionnaires stated that the students were interested in using videos in class to improve their learning outcomes. It is visible from the literature review that most of the work done is focused on Youtube videos, and very little is focused on other social media platforms for video sharing such as TikTok, Snapchat or Instagram TV. We believe that this gap needs to be filled by the research community. In the same thread, adding subtitles to a video can have both positive and negative affect; therefore, it is important to distinguish when to use subtitles while teaching a FL.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Foreign language education and technology are not strangers to each other. The acquisition of a foreign language (FL) has merged as one of the main goals in a global economy and an increasingly multilingual society. Ravichandran, Kretovics, Kirby, and Ghosh (2017) mention that writing and public speaking are two of the most daunting obstacles for students to tackle while studying a foreign language. Students are anxious because they are afraid of making mistakes. It has a solid link to their self-esteem being affected when learning a foreign language.

According to Kavitha and Jain (n.d.) & Le (2021), the Internet has emerged as a popular emerging technology in recent years. The impact of such a powerful technological tool has spread across our world's educational, industry, and economic sectors. The Internet is commonly listed, regardless of one's familiarity with it. Whether or not one uses the Internet, it is necessary to realize that we have reached a new information age, and the Internet is here to stay. Since the Internet is used in so many different fields and domains, it has many potentials for educational use, especially in second and foreign language education.

Furthermore, in recent years, Web 2.0 technology has allowed millions of people worldwide to connect and communicate in various ways. A recent study by Barrot (2021) mentions that Web 2.0 applications, indeed, exploit the Web's participatory ability. Consequently, Web 2.0 connectivity has become an essential component of many students' everyday and academic lives.

Tens of thousands of educators have begun experimenting with the resources given by Web 2.0, and this pattern is no exception in the field of the second language (L2) education. Therefore, it can be concluded that the future effect of Web 2.0 technology on language learning and teaching is groundbreaking Wang and Vásquez (2012) & AŞIKSOY (2018).

For instance, Web 2.0 sites like YouTube have grown in popularity since their launch, with over 100,000 videos made and shared every day Baharudin, Ghazali, and Halias (n.d.).

In contrast to reading texts, writing tasks, and listening exercises, a video has a significant advantage in that it is immediately engaging. Students of all ages are drawn to film, and many view it as a treat when used in class. Additionally, one of the most important benefits of using videos as a learning method is to inspire students. For many learners, understanding a natural person speaking a language is a significant accomplishment (Prayuda, Lindawati, and Mustopa (2021)).

Moreover, in contrast to reading texts and listening practices, video with subtitles offers clear visual cues. These aid learners in comprehending what is going on, even though the language is difficult to understand. Furthermore, the video provides limitless opportunities for learners to be exposed to various accents and dialects. Students will learn about diverse cultures, new locations, and ideas through watching videos. Besides, video content with subtitles can be beneficial in FL classes. While subtitles have been criticized for being distracting or a source of passivity in students, we should now recognize that they are far from being a source of passivity.

P. Yang (2020) mentions that subtitles, on the other hand, could have the ability to aid the learning process by providing learners with access to vast amounts of authentic and comprehensible language input. Indeed, text in the form of subtitles aids learners in keeping track of expression that would otherwise be lost. In reality, while unsubtitled TV shows and films can cause students to feel insecure and anxious, subtitles provide immediate feedback and positive reinforcement, building a sense of trust in learners, allowing them to feel prepared and encouraged to watch international television films and other media.

This study explores the current state of research on videos and L2 learning, investigates the theoretical perspectives framing the recent research, and identifies some of the benefits of using video content with subtitles and captions on L2 education, and pinpoint possible limitations in the existing research. This study is also designed to propose possible directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

In addition to focusing on the traditional four language skills, researchers have looked at culture, literacy, peer feedback, participation, dialogue, knowledge building, communication skills, and instructional method comparisons (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). Learner attitudes and desires, personalities, motivation, autonomy, and learning cultures have all been studied by researchers. Within the third technology division, researchers compared the effect of various technological resources on L2 learning.

In conclusion, the language learning environments provided by Web 2.0 advances have helped to broaden the scope of technology and language learning research, which had previously been limited to the four traditional language skills. New contexts for exploring new literacies, genres, personalities, and pedagogies have emerged due to Web 2.0 learning environments (Cong-Lem (2018)).

In this regard, various studies have investigated this integration. A survey by Brook (2011) examines how YouTube can be a tool to facilitate language learning and teaching and confidence-building and increase authenticity, student-centred activities with increased participation.

Another research looked at international student's perceptions and understanding of the role of information and communication technology (ICT) in learning English and overcoming language barriers (Kuddus and Khan (2021)). The study's goal was to see how ICT could help international students at the University of India develop their English language skills. A survey was administered, and international students were asked questions.

The study's results indicate that students use synchronous and asynchronous mediums to improve their language skills, such as smartphone apps, subtitled movies, games, and YouTube. Furthermore, students tend to learn the language passively, at their speed and in their room, rather than actively involved in the process.

A study is presented by Tarchi, Zaccoletti, and Mason (2021) to see how media (text, video, or subtitled video) affected students' learning outcomes. Previous research has raised questions about the efficacy of online videos over content-equivalent texts for learning. Furthermore, subtitled videos add to the educational burden. In a pretest, post-test, and delayed post-test design, 247 undergraduate students were randomly assigned to a text, video, or subtitled-video condition. The topic was stem cells.

Comprehension and learning results were assessed using literal, inferential, and transition questions. The study's findings verified the significant equivalence of all situations in terms of immediate comprehension. On the other hand, the results confirmed the drawback of subtitled videos in profound learning outcomes.

Razali and Halim (2021) perform a study in a secondary school setting. The first target assesses students' attitudes toward the use of YouTube videos in learning Present Perfect Tense in terms of the elements of 1) interesting, 2) appropriate, 3) helpful, 4) motivation inside the classroom, and 5) motivation outside the school. The second goal examines the elements of YouTube videos that foster student interest in learning *Present Perfect Tense*. In contrast, the third goal investigates the benefits and drawbacks of using YouTube videos to learn *Present Perfect Tense*. This qualitative research involved the participation of seven students, all of whom were 15 years old. Data was gathered from the students through semi-structured interviews and classroom observations.

The findings show that students have a positive attitude toward using YouTube to learn *Present Perfect Tense*. The different stimuli combinations have helped to engage students behaviorally, emotionally, and cognitively. Furthermore, videos such as acts, subtitles, and narrator have led to students' interaction with the lesson.

The effect of adding text to videos on English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners' listening comprehension is examined by Alabsi (2020). The participants were 76 Taibah University prep college EFL students who were split into two classes. The experimental group and the control group were compared using the semi-experimental measure. The experimental group watched an English learning video, used apps to create text subtitles for the video, and then took a listening test to determine their comprehension of information from the videos.

During live lectures, the control group watched videos but did not add subtitles to the content they were watching. The level of listening comprehension achievement was assessed using a paired samples t-test, and the findings were compared. The results showed a statistically significant improvement in listening comprehension. The results showed that teaching/learning through video watching and adding text apps resulted in superior output and a substantial positive effect.

Regarding the psychological and cognitive benefits of using videos in foreign language learning, P. Yang (2020) use YouTube videos and text help modes, emphasizing the impact captioning and subtitling YouTube videos have on intermediate-high and advanced German language learners. The study finds that captioning has a more positive effect on intermediate-high and advanced German learners' motivation, owing to more efficient language processing. Also, the videos can provide linguistic credibility, allowing language learners to concentrate their incidental attention effectively. The findings provide valuable insights into and enthusiasm for the effective use of YouTube videos to develop higher-level German courses and hopefully contribute to establishing best practices in this emerging area.

Putri, Wijayanto, and Supriyadi (2020) present the idea of using YouTube for learning English. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate EFL students' perceptions of self-regulated learning using YouTube and the strengths and disadvantages of this method. The approach used in this analysis is a case study, which was used to achieve the research's goal. In-depth interviews were used to gather data for this study. The subjects of this study were four undergraduate students from an Indonesian university majoring in English education, who were intentionally chosen to provide adequate details.

The findings of this study revealed that students have positive attitudes toward EFL students who use YouTube to self-regulate their learning. They claimed that using YouTube could help them control their English learning and give them joy, pleasure, and excitement during the learning process. Furthermore, the strengths of self-regulated learning using YouTube were discovered in this study, including YouTube's abundance of learning materials, ease of use, and versatility of time and place when using YouTube to control their learning. Meanwhile, financial restrictions and a lack of Internet access are drawbacks.

Other social media platforms, e.g., TikTok, are also becoming popular among many people worldwide. In this regard, H. Yang (2020) starts by investigating secondary school students' expectations of using TikTok for English learning outside the classroom. 187 Chinese secondary school students volunteered to participate in the quantitative survey study, which used an online questionnaire as the research tool.

The findings showed that secondary-school students were enthusiastic about using TikTok as a video aid in EFL classrooms while also using it as an English learning strategy outside of class. Furthermore, students expressed a deep desire for their teachers to encourage them to use TikTok effectively for English learning.

In a similar thread, the ability to listen and comprehend plays a vital role, as well. When EFL students are introduced to videos, they may have difficulty using this ability, which means that their language learning process will be slowed. Intralingual subtitles are one of the methods students may use to enhance their listening comprehension.

Therefore, Fares and Azeroual (2020) explore the different attitudes of both teachers and students toward using intralingual subtitles to overcome listening comprehension problems. It was hypothesized that teachers and students positively attitude toward using intralingual subtitles in videos to overcome students' listening comprehension problems. An online questionnaire was given to 40 first-year students and 17 English department teachers at Larbi Ben M'hidi University, Oum El Bouaghi, to test the hypothesis and collect the current analysis data.

Both teachers and students had a good outlook about using intralingual subtitles recordings. Both agreed that captions would help students solve listening comprehension issues, according to the results of both questionnaires. As a result, using such a cutting-edge tool as a pedagogical aid in foreign language learning/teaching merits further attention and understanding.

The use of videos in language learning has been studied in the literature to improve second language acquisition. Previous research has looked into the impact of videos on foreign language learning, especially vocabulary learning. Qadha and Alward (2020) aim to look in to the effect of video on learning present progressive tense from a semiotics standpoint. The study enlisted 30 Arab EFL students divided in to two classes. With recordings, the first group was taught the *present progressive tense* (the semiotics group). The

second group was led to the same material more conventionally, without the use of recordings. The post-test revealed that participants in the semiotics community outperformed those who did not learn the *present progressive tense* through recordings. The study concluded that using videos to improve *present progressive tense* learning is a good idea.

Another study by Baharudin et al. (n.d.) aims to assess the degree to which the YouTube application is used to teach Arabic listening skills and respondents' impressions of the different types of YouTube materials that have been selected and collected. This survey study used a questionnaire instrument to assess the degree of YouTube application used to teach Arabic listening skills to students and examine students' impressions of the materials chosen. The study sample consisted of 70 students from a Malaysian public university chosen randomly. A series of questionnaires covering different aspects of YouTube application use in T&L Arabic language skills were used to collect data. According to the results, students are more likely to be drawn to materials with exciting shapes, graphics, audios and visuals, and acceptable timeframes.

Prayuda et al. (2021) aim to study the teacher's experience teaching English in the classroom using YouTube videos as a medium and the students' experiences learning English in class using YouTube videos as a medium. The research design used by the researcher in this study is mixed methods with a convergent parallel design style. Interviews and questionnaires were used as data collection tools by the researcher.

The findings of this study revealed that using YouTube videos in class benefits both teachers and students. It can be shown by the results of teacher interviews, which revealed that using YouTube videos in the classroom aids the learning process. Furthermore, the survey's findings revealed that students were interested in using YouTube videos.

Al Harbi (2021) investigates the use of social media (YouTube and Snapchat) as a teach-in tool to improve EFL Saudi students' listening comprehension skills. The researcher used a mixed-method approach that included a questionnaire and a post-test to ensure the research's validity to accomplish this goal. A total of 50 female students from Taif University's English Language Centre took part in the study. The study results revealed that using social media (YouTube and Snapchat) would help Saudi EFL learners improve their listening skills. According to the authors of this study, more research should be done on other samples from various studies, age groups, and different backgrounds, such as schools or training institutes.

For informal FL learning, a study by Dizon (n.d.) looked into the activities of Japanese university students who use subscription video streaming services (SVSSs) for informal FL learning and their attitudes toward using these resources for informal FL learning. A survey was given to second-language English students at four Japanese universities to achieve the study's objectives. Besides, semi-structured interviews with 12 participants were conducted to learn more about their perspectives on SVSSs for FL learning. A total of 256 students took part in the survey and completed it thoroughly.

The findings show that FL students use SVSSs for informal FL learning and have positive attitudes regarding language learning. These results emphasize the importance of looking at students' digital habits, such as video streaming, to close the difference between informal language learning outside of the classroom and formal language learning.

3. Raised awareness and possible re-positioning

Language learning can be more entertaining, inspiring, and collaborative with Web 2.0 tools and their interactive, social, and collaborative functionality. As mentioned earlier and their results, the state-of-the-art indicate that integrating video content resources has great potential to benefit language learning and teaching by multiple means.

Also, video content can be used in several different phases of a language learning course, such as brainstorming, presentation, practice, testing, and so on, to engage and motivate students in a learner-centred approach.

Since there is a wide range of video-sharing websites on the Internet, including video lessons, documentaries, and educational content, both humanistic and scientific subjects may benefit from the use of videos.

Videos may also be used to teach other subjects to low-level learners in a foreign language. To help learners develop listening and comprehension techniques, it is essential to assess their needs, level of competence, and context knowledge. As

a result, any lesson planning should be driven by a careful collection and appropriate use of visual materials. However, according to Cinganotto and Cuccurullo (2015), subtitling or videos with captions in a lesson has proven ineffective and distracting, as students' attention would be drawn to the written text than the material.

4. Possible interventions

Learning with web 2.0 has clearly illustrated positive effects for learning and inclusion, as shown by increased accessibility and accessibility of hard-to-reach learning opportunities, increased motivation and interest in learning participation, overall skills and competencies, and positive impacts on social integration.

In terms of Web 2.0 applications, we want to promote a new viewpoint that will facilitate future research into the interaction and interrelation of video content. For example, the real value of YouTube - at least in terms of language learning - provides genuine examples of everyday English spoken by ordinary people. Simultaneously, teachers can use YouTube videos to link students to the “real life” essence. Students may be assisted in exploring a landscape of online learning possibilities by providing meaning for these short videos. In an ELT classroom, YouTube videos can teach vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation, and other subjects.

On the possible contributions of videos to language learning, research is still in its early stages. More research is required to see whether other factors, including gender, age, the field of study, computer literacy, and learner personality, influence video content.

Additionally, the benefit of subtitles is that the student hears the speech and is not bored because he or she completely comprehends the sense of what is being said. The downside is that unless the student’s language proficiency is adequate, they will not link the spoken and written words. Students will waste a lot of time watching videos with subtitles without making any progress. This is why subtitles are commonly used as supplemental content, a motivational aid, or something to show students the beauty of the language they want to learn.

Subtitles make matching oral and written forms of words much more straightforward, enabling students to break up the flow of speech into different chunks. Students hear stories and see them on a computer, which helps them develop their reading comprehension, listening skills, phonetics, spelling, and, indirectly, grammar understanding by introducing them to grammar patterns. However, they are of little benefit to elementary and pre-intermediate students since the video contains many unfamiliar terms and grammar constructs that make it difficult for them to understand. As a result, they lose interest in the film, their focus moves to something else, and their motivation to pursue their studies fades. As a result, the teacher must wait until students reach the intermediate stage before implementing the strategy.

Therefore, there is still a lot of work to be done, especially in assessing its effectiveness. Special studies may be done to compare students using traditional textbooks to students who have increased their vocabulary, improved their grammar, reading, and listening comprehension over time.

As a result, we believe that more work needs to be done to strengthen accreditation processes and practices. This may assist in bridging the gap between it and the conventional educational establishment.

The right partnerships and the necessary amounts of sustainable funding are required to support the advancement of initiatives, such as video content and video-blogging. To feed into future business models and policy initiatives to promote more development, more research is needed to gather evidence of cost-effectiveness.

5. Conclusion

Video content has a beneficial impact on student learning when used constructively and creatively as part of the learning process. It improves listening skills to better understand and comprehend on a more advanced level. It also helps with anxiety and trust when studying a foreign language. Learning with videos was relevant and encouraging for the students, and it was also inherently conducive to providing visual feedback to teachers. Videos are well known for their ability to increase interaction.

Nonetheless, we are left with the impression that learning with video can facilitate curricular integration as a tool, is accessible to teachers, can be used in various ways, and provides incentives for student participation and improved listening skills. For the most part, blogging seems to be both an encouraging activity and one that can boost the ability of both teachers to provide constructive input and the writing skills of students.

Moreover, using videos with subtitles or caption can also improve reading skills simultaneously. Students can continue watching the videos without losing interest in the video when there is a complex grammar structure. However, it should be carefully employed not to become involved with subtitles and lose the listening exercise rather than just focusing on the subtitles.

Therefore, we advocate that further work is needed to strengthen the processes and requirements of accreditation using video content for teaching a foreign language. That can help to bridge the gaps between it and the conventional education establishment.

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